

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMPOSITE HORIZONTAL STABILIZER FOR A FIGHTER AIRCRAFT

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SUMMARY: An advanced composite horizontal stabilizer has been developed for a newly designed fighter. The building block and concurrent engineering methodology was followed in this work. Under the constraints of stiffness, material, and maintenance, etc., the structure was optimized for weight reduction with sophisticated manufacturing methods. The assembled structure were certified by dynamic test, static test, and damage tolerance tests. The natural frequency, mode shape and damping ratio were measured during the dynamic test. In addition, the strength and stiffness of the structure were determined by the static test. The load spectrum was applied in the horizontal stabilizer fatigue test for two life times. After flush bonded boron/epoxy patching and flush bolted titanium patching repairs for the simulated damages, one more life time fatigue test was carried out. The development work has been successfully finished with unique composite corrugated understructure and certified to the military requirements. The horizontal stabilizer has been subjected to series production.

KEYWORDS: composite horizontal stabilizer, static test, dynamic test, damage tolerance, delamination, patching, inspection interval, barely visible impact damage

INTRODUCTION

To ensure that a newly developed major structure of an aircraft meets the design requirements, a series of analyses and tests ,including static strength, ground vibration, damage tolerance and flight test[1], should be performed. Laminated composites, with their high strength - to -weight ratio, offer considerable technological advances in the production of aircraft structures. In general, graphite-epoxy composites have the advantage of resistance to cracking by spectrum loading and immunity to corrosion. However, design is complex due to the nonhomogeneous nature of the material and its failure modes. For example, the delaminations in the composite skins could result in stiffness and strength loss, thereby reducing the flutter resistance and strength margin of the structures. Since that no general rules of testing for composite structures are available, sometimes individual procedures adapted to the structure has to be developed[2].

The requirements of safety, original weight, size and maintenance for large-scale composite structure is much more importance than that of small-scale composite structure. In order to develop a newly designed large-scale composite structure successfully, team-work is especially important. The development of composite horizontal stabilizer involves all kinds of specialty. Detail considerations have to be made in every steps during the designing and manufacturing process by means of concurrent engineering. In this manuscript, the

certification procedures of the assembled composite horizontal stabilizer of a fighter was discussed through the introductions of design concept, analyses and tests.

STRUCTURAL DESCRIPTION

The major structural elements of the composite horizontal stabilizer shown in Fig.1 are: 1) composite upper and lower skins, 2) composite sine wave corrugated substructure, 3) metallic leading edge and trailing edge, 4) metallic tip rib and root rib. The upper and lower composite skins were made of Fiberite T300/976 Gr/Ep prepreg. The skin were symmetric to each other and were designed as quasi-isotropic stacking sequence with 0° , 45° , 90° and -45° in about equal proportions. The zero direction of fiber was arranged along the spanwise direction. The laminate thickness varies from 16 plies near the tip of the horizontal stabilizer to 64 plies near the region of the pivot shaft. In contrast to a plane plate, the stability of the corrugated plate was influenced by many parameters including angle of corrugate, radius of corrugate, overall plate dimension and thickness of the laminate. The horizontal stabilizer is classified as a safety-of-flight structure. Skins, corrugated substructure and metallic pivot shaft are assembled with bolts and rivets.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

Since complex load paths are prone to fracture, especially the places with stress concentration, these regions are the candidate points for damage tolerance analysis and test. Based on the analysis results, once the thickness and percentage distribution can be obtained, the stacking sequence can be determined. The objective of the stress analysis is to provide the correct internal forces and load path for selection of impact locations. The analysis flowchart, shown in Fig.2., includes dynamic analysis, static analysis and damage tolerance analysis. In addition, an analysis had been made of the probable lightning strike zones of the fighter, guiding the design of lightning protection material. Considering that the metallic tip rib can act as a good conductor for releasing the lightning energy, no severe lightning damage will be expected on the skins.

To attain a perfect design of a composite structure, the concept of design and manufacture must be considered in all respects as shown in Fig.3. There are some special requirements to be fulfilled which made the design of the horizontal stabilizer a tough job. These requirements include weight reduction, performance promotion, cost effective, maintenance, strength, stiffness and life limit. Also, some design considerations have to be taken into account such as the source of material, configuration of the structure, operate environment, equipment capacity, schedule, budget, and quality assurance ability. The design flowchart is shown in Fig.4. Before the formal production start not only ground test but also flight test have to be implemented to certify that the design requirements were met. In the following paragraphs, only the materials and processes and the ground test which includes dynamic test, static test and damage tolerance test are introduced.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

The material chosen should satisfy the application requirements of sustaining temperature 115°C , hot/wet properties at 100°C and the mechanic properties loss less than 5% in the environment of salt water, hydraulic oil, fuel(JP-4) and solvent. The material was qualified

according to the physical and mechanical requirements specified in the material specification. For the sake of structure design and analysis, the design allowables was established by the material coupon tests subjected to environment, fatigue, stress concentration and damage tolerance effects for the quasi-isotropic laminates.

The process specification was developed for the fabrication of composite stabilizer. The prepreg patterns were provided by the automatic cutting machine using CATIA design data. The skins and corrugated substructure were made by the autoclave curing of vacuum bagged lay-ups using the composite tooling. In this specification, the curing cycle, process qualification tests, and the non-destructive tests were also described and implemented during the production.

TEST PROCEDURES

The full scale tests are influenced by numerous factors; for example, test procedures and boundary conditions of the test article. To get a realistic result for the structural capacity, these factors have to be clarified and defined. All the full scale test must be proceeded by tests of components to get the test parameters. The completion and review of these parameters was done by test of substructure, the bending - torsion box (B.T. box)[2], to reach the realistic test procedure to be performed in the full scale test.

The test items during the development of the composite horizontal stabilizer are shown in Fig.5. The real structural natural frequency, mode shapes and damping ratio were obtained from dynamic test. By setting the exciter at the proper locations, the response can be read out from the accelerometers. After the process of filtering, amplification and calculation of signal, the test results were then compared with the analytical results. The tested article can be suspended independently, or can be set on a fixture. Also, it can be put on the full scale airplane for testing with more real boundary simulation. The purposes of static test are : 1) verify the correctness of the analysis results, 2) to obtain the real strength of the tested structure, 3) to fulfill the requirements according to the specifications. Similar to the damage tolerance test, the strain gages should be adhered to the critical locations. The simulation of the boundary conditions is one of the key points of making a good test.

To get realistic information for the design base for the horizontal stabilizer, for instance from the damage tolerance respect, attention has to be paid to the impact test parameters on specimens or components, including impact energy, type of impactor, geometry, support conditions, material properties, specimen thickness, stacking sequence and loads. The purpose of the impact pretests is to verify the input parameters of testing the horizontal stabilizer under the realistic boundary conditions. The procedure and performance steps are as follows. First, selection of the critical areas of the horizontal stabilizer. Second, definition of test point geometry and support conditions. Third, definition of the test parameters such as impact energies and impactor size and form. Finally, damage size was measurement by A-scan as function of the impactor type and energy. The results of the impact pretests defined the reference data for the damage tolerance tests of the horizontal stabilizer. Of all the damage types which are possible during manufacture and service, delaminations, impact damage, lightning strike damage, battle damage and loose rivets were selected for damage tolerance test because of their important effects on structural capacity.

Since the artificial flaws of comparable area to impact damage produce less reduction in compressive strength[5], also considering the estimated expenditure, delaminations were simulated by serious impact damage only. There were 25 damaged-locations, including 13

barely visible impact damage (BVID), 8 visible impact damage (VID), 1 lightning strike damage, 1 battle damage and 2 loose rivets. Considering that the delamination is prone to spread under compressive loading, most of the damage (14 locations) was applied to the lower skin.

To certify the feasibility and reliability of repair technology on composite structures, two impact damaged-areas were repaired after two lifetimes of damage tolerance test. Both flush composite bonded repair and metal bolted repair were applied to the composite lower skin. Finally, on completion of four lifetimes of damage tolerance test, a static residual strength test was performed to check whether structural strength after repair implementation met the requirements. Stiffness and static strength of the composite horizontal stabilizer with and without damage were evaluated and compared.

The critical load case has to be decided together with the detailed damage locations. The load types can be expected to be the same as those for the B.T. box. The results of the impact pretest and parameters investigated by the B.T. box test defined the reference data for the damage tolerance tests of the horizontal stabilizer. According to the specifications[3,4], two design lifetimes of damage tolerance test should be performed. However, considering that the composite structure is sensitive to environmental change, which is difficult to simulate in the test laboratory for a full-scale article, the first lifetime damage tolerance test with BVID defects was carried out to assess environmental effects[2]. For the following two lifetimes of test, visible impact damage, large delaminations, lightning strike and loose rivets were applied to the horizontal stabilizer to assess the damage tolerance characteristics. Finally, one lifetime testing with magnitude of load increased to 14% was carried out to evaluate the possibilities for extending the service life of the horizontal stabilizer. Totally, the test article was subjected to four lifetimes of flight - by - flight load spectra simulating the in-service fatigue loading condition for the aircraft.

INSPECTION AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

The quality assurance people should not only execute the inspection during test, but also has to prepare for the quality assurance plan. From general inspection point of view, the inspection items involved from the beginning of material screening to the final production step, as shown in Fig.6. The major inspection work during the development of composite horizontal stabilizer is the inspection of damages during and after the damage tolerance test. During this test, strain surveys and NDI (non-destructive inspection) were carried out periodically to monitor strain distribution and to record damage growth. The exact positions to be impacted, especially at the ply termination, can be identified by measuring the thickness of the laminate with the help of portable NDI (A-scan). In addition, any existing manufacturing defects around the impact positions must be detected. Again, NDI was utilized to determine the extent of the internal damage of the structure after impact. Strain surveys and NDI inspections were taken periodically to track the strain history and damage growth.

VERIFICATION

Static strength tests of the composite horizontal stabilizer, the final and most important test item, aimed at investigating the influences of damage on structure stiffness and strength and also prove the strength of repairs. To simulate a better design limit load condition, 13 load

actuators, and the offset concept which allow the actuators to adjust their loading direction were used. For composite horizontal stabilizer without damage, the static strength attains 175% design limit load. Tensile failure modes were found at the bolted region of upper skin and pivot fitting. For the composite horizontal stabilizer with 23 damaged-areas and 2 repairs, the residual static strength attains 160% limit load, which meets the regulation , i.e. the damaged horizontal stabilizer structure must be capable of sustaining limit load without any failure or obvious partial failure. Also, two repaired regions were survived after being subjected to 160% limit load, hence structure with damage of the tested sizes and locations is repairable.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the structural certification of dynamic character, static strength and damage tolerance strength in developing the composite horizontal stabilizer of a fighter. Test items include ground vibration tests, static test, and simulation of damage of composite structure by four lifetime test of flight-by-flight load spectra. Conclusions from these tests can be summarized below :

- (1) Damage to composite structure was more difficult to simulate than that of metallic structure. Very often, there are no general rules of testing for composite structures available, individual procedures adapted to the structure has to be developed.
- (2) The test results indicated that the development of the composite horizontal stabilizer is quite a success. The design is optimal and the requirements are met. The test results also provides an important reference for service maintenance.
- (3) To develop an advanced composite horizontal stabilizer, new techniques such as structural health monitoring and co-cured manufacturing could be some possible fields for researches in the future.

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Fig.1 Composite Horizontal Stabilizer Components

Fig.2 Structure Analysis Flowchart

Fig.3. Design requirements and Limitations of Composite structure

Fig.4 Composite Structure Development Flowchart

Fig.5 Test item during composite H.T. development

Fig.6 Quality Guarantee And Test